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Project Acronym: MONPLAS

Project title: Monitoring Micro- and Nanoplastics

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

High-Throughput Inertial Microfluidics for Micro-Nanoplastics Enrichment

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History of edits:		
Version	Date	Amendments:
v1.0	19.05.2021	Initial DMP draft based on DMPonline
<i>vN+1</i>		<i>e.g. Treat all RESEARCH OUTPUTS as FAIR & open “data”</i>
<i>vN+2</i>		<i>e.g. Explore converting DMP to machine actionable DMP</i>

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Template: Horizon 2020 DMP

Project abstract:

During this doctoral project, the first goal is developing high-throughput inertial microfluidic systems that enable the separation of micro- and nanoplastics from water and other mediums such as beverages based on inertial focusing which will provide passive, label-free and cost-effective separation method. Since the inertial microfluidic is based on the physics and geometry of the system, there will not be a need for using an external field to induce the force. The created inertial microfluidic system will be characterised using micro- and nanoparticles. In addition, different samples from various locations that will be provided thanks to the MONPLAS ITN consortium can be tried in the system. Depending on the results, the design of the microfluidic system can be changed and optimised in order to separate particles as desired. Not only experimental results but also simulations will be used to test the system as well. It is important to keep in mind that the physical interactions of micro-plastics and nano-plastics in the water or any other medium are different from each other. A created inertial microfluidic system that may work perfectly for separating micro-plastics from water may not work for separating nano-plastics from water. Therefore, the second goal in the project is creating another microfluidic system that uses the acoustic waves to induce the force for separating nano-plastics from water. A new system will be designed, integrated with the acoustic field and characterised for the separation purposes. If it is possible, it is aimed to use the same system for separating micro- and nanoplastics from water. This may be achieved creating a dynamic system for the separation. After successful separation, the final goal of the project is integrating machine learning into the project for creating new designs that can be used for several applications in biology, health and environment in the future. The experimental and simulation data that will be produced throughout the project can be used to feed the algorithm.

Last modified: 19-05-2021

MONPLAS - Initial DMP

1. Data summary

Provide a summary of the data addressing the following issues:

State the purpose of the data collection/generation

Explain the relation to the objectives of the project

Specify the types and formats of data generated/collected

Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any)

Specify the origin of the data

State the expected size of the data (if known)

Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful

- The data will be collected to understand the micro and nano plastics positioning in the water and then it can be used to separate micro- and nanoplastics from water.
- It will allow us to create a novel design for inertial microfluidic devices.
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Type	Volume	Storage	Format
Literature	MB	Hard Drive	.pdf
Images	GB	Hard Drive KTH Repository	.tif .png
Reports	MB	Hard Drive MONPLAS and KTH Repository	.docx .pdf
Presentations	MB	Hard Drive MONPLAS Repository	.pptx
Microfluidics Design (AUTOCAD)	MB	Hard Drive MONPLAS and KTH Repository	.dxf
Fabrication Protocols	MB	Hard Drive MONPLAS and KTH Repository ZENODO	.docx
Machine Learning Algorithms	MB	Hard Drive Github	.py
Research Papers	MB	Hard Drive ZENODO KTH Library Journals Repository	.pdf .txt

- Some existing protocols and designs for microfluidics

- Experimental data will be originated from Fluorescence microscope, AUTOCAD, COMSOL, Python, Raman, FTIR in most of the times. Presentations, protocols and reports will be created using Microsoft Power Point and Word. Excel will be used for creating tabular forms.
- 1 TB (rough estimation)
- MONPLAS consortium, scientists from inertial microfluidics field will benefit from data which will be produced throughout the project.

2. FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

Outline the discoverability of data (metadata provision)

Outline the identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism. Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers?

Outline naming conventions used

Outline the approach towards search keyword

Outline the approach for clear versioning

Specify standards for metadata creation (if any). If there are no standards in your discipline describe what metadata will be created and how

- Open metadata is a priority to be resolved for next version following community standards where they exist. Microfluidics fabrication protocols can be published in protocols.io
- DOI numbers can be the basis for the identifiability of data.
- It is important to be consistent and descriptive in naming and organising files. Date and short description are key elements to be considered in a naming convention. The standard in naming is YYYY-MM-DD_ExperimentName. In addition, other key information regarding the experiment such as sample size, chip type, Re value etc. is saved in .xml format under the name of ExperimentBook. This file also contains the date information and the number of the experiment.
- Standard ontologies and vocabularies will be priority for next version, following further research.
- While versioning, the file will follow the same rules as naming. In addition, v1, v2.1 can be added to the name to show the different versions. Significant changes in various versions will be added to the .xml file as well.
- Metadata will be created after using fluorescence microscope containing information about the user, microscope settings and positions and stored in .xml or text files.

2.2 Making data openly accessible:

Specify which data will be made openly available? If some data is kept closed provide rationale for doing so

Specify how the data will be made available

Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited

Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions

- Simulation and Image Data, some data in tabular form will be open. KTH-Zenodo can be the place for sharing data.
- Github can be used for short-term archiving. KTH researchers can upload their data to the Zenodo through the KTH-Zenodo community. The data can be issued with DOI and associated with KTH. The quality of the data will be reviewed by the KTH research data office. Zenodo is compatible with Github as well.
- ImageJ and COMSOL, for designs CAD programs, for tabular data Excel
- Institute library. The data location can be obtained from a provided link
- After getting the permissions from the institute, the data will be accessible

2.3 Making data interoperable:

Assess the interoperability of your data. Specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability.

Specify whether you will be using standard vocabulary for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability? If not, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

- Metadata is a priority to be resolved for next version following community standards where they exist.
- For inertial microfluidics, there are no ontologies. Standard ontologies and vocabularies will be priority for next version, following further research.

2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses):

Specify how the data will be licenced to permit the widest reuse possible

Specify when the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed

Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why

Describe data quality assurance processes

Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable

- Initially, the data can be categorized as reusable and non-reusable. For the reusable data a license should be associated and shared afterwards.
- The data will be shared at the publication and if it is applicable, it can be reused.
- If the data is considered as usable and will not be used for patenting, then it can be reused.
- Peer-review and institute intercommunication
- 5 years and longer

3. Allocation of resources

Explain the allocation of resources, addressing the following issues:

Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. Describe how you intend to cover these costs

Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project

Describe costs and potential value of long-term preservation

- Estimated costs is 1-month full time equivalent over 36 months. Costs will be covered through MONPLAS and KTH funds.
- PIs Aman Russom, Håkan Jönsson and PhD Student Selim Tanriverdi
- About 6000 euro for three peer-reviewed publications during the fellowship. In addition to this, KTH IT-support can provide extended storage and cost of this service can be calculated by IT-support if needed at a later stage.

KTH Library can be helpful for making data FAIR.

4. Data security

Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data

The data that is usable for us for publication such as designs, images, etc. will be archived in the institute. KTH IT-security can provide a secure storage. Each employee at KTH has access to BOX storage that can be used with external partners as well. Additionally, Zenodo can be used as described before.

5. Ethical aspects

To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former

There will be no personal data in the project.

6. Other

Refer to other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management that you are using (if any)

Swedish law for archiving and MONPLAS consortium

AMBITION for DATA MANAGEMENT:

The ultimate ambition for this DMP is to maintain a “***living document***” as a research tool, that supports ***optimal transparency, reproducibility*** and ***re-use*** of all research ***outputs*** by ***aiming at 100% disclosure*** by end of project.

Ultimately, this Data Management Plan (v1.0) should evolve into a ***Digital Outputs Management Plan***, treating all research outputs of this project as “***data***”, and seeking open file formats, open protocols and pipeline to ***make all outputs FAIR and Open***, in full synergy with the MONPLAS Disclosure protocols, and Intellectual Property Right (IPR) exploitation, by referring to MONPLAS Exploitation Management Committee & the Dissemination Committee.

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